

Edge Hill University

Development of a Machine Learning Software Platform to aid in completing predictive maintenance on consumer automotive vehicles.

CIS3140 CW2 – Project Report

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Abstract

This project developed a predictive maintenance solution for consumers and garages where a machine learning module was trained and developed on top of an exhaustive United Kingdom MOT data set. The model utilises classifiers to predict and set indicators on consumer vehicles when they may be about to experience a failure in a test and pre-emptively deliver this to them so their vehicle can be checked over beforehand saving time, money and improving safety.

Chapter 1 Introduction

A personal vehicle means a lot to a person and provides them with freedom and accessibility until a breakdown occurs. Breakdowns can occur out of the blue due to rapidly changing conditions of roads, but they often happen from an accumulation of mistreatment and lack of servicing. These vehicles are an element of most people's lives which are depended upon but often grossly neglected due to both misinformation and a lack of knowledge. Due to this lack of understanding with vehicles, they are often left until they present errors or until a mandatory MOT Test takes place leading to both time and money being wasted.

As with most maintenance, vehicle maintenance can be accomplished in one of three alternative methods: reactive, proactive, and predictive (Ahern, Dominic and Bruton, 2022). Reactive maintenance is therefore the choice of most consumers as it is believed that frequent servicing of vehicles can be seen as a preventable waste of these resources. Reactive maintenance refers to the aforementioned idea that a vehicle has already experienced a major safety issue due to a failing part. However, when these issues occur they can often cause an onset of damage to other components or place the users' lives at risk (IBM, 2024). Proactive maintenance is the idea that the vehicle is maintained when a fault begins to develop – this method is the second most common choice of a consumer. For instance, when a dashboard warning light appears or a new sound happens to catch the driver's attention, this is when a proactive maintenance approach would be taking it to a garage to be looked over to correct faults at the point of their failure. This is typically a less popular option due to a culture of untrusted mechanics and a firm belief that this wastes money if more mileage can be given from the car before a part entirely fails (Santos and Daniel, 2008). Predictive maintenance is an element that is not at all seen within the consumer market for vehicles. In recent years, predictive maintenance has become paramount for commercial vehicles and highly sensitive, time-critical environments such as Formula 1 racing (Exner et al., 2017). Predictive maintenance in these commercial sectors saves significant time, and money and most importantly improves health and safety reducing the risk of injury or death significantly (Calixto, 2016).

With the milestones and benefits seen in these sectors, a gap in the market of aiding the consumer vehicle market with predictive analysis of their vehicles could potentially see a significant decrease in injury and death due to instances such as breakdowns in a live lane of a motorway or prevent a critical structural component from failing on a dangerous road. As previously mentioned, the benefits of an easily accessible system to help prevent these issues are saving time, and money, preventing the scrapping of entire cars and helping to provide users with peace of mind for their vehicles.

The creation of a system which is applicable in this sector will be overseen for the duration of the following report. This project creates a system using publicly accessible data for vehicles in the United Kingdom and adheres to recommendations and Machine Learning models based on

safety specifications in this region. As usage patterns vary greatly depending on vehicles and users, training an accurate machine learning model for this project means that conclusions are subjective but can be improved with further data collection. This final iteration of a web-based machine learning platform uses a widening variety of methods, programming languages and prototypes to ensure compatibility and accessibility for a widening audience of consumers.

The purpose of this software solution is not only to help consumers make informed choices by using a machine learning model but also to bridge the gap between consumers and mechanics. Having a software platform that allows for a cross-platform vehicle management system between vehicle owners and their garages should help to increase confidence in the services offered and as a result, allow for predictive maintenance to be carried out more frequently in the form of services and regular vehicle checks.

Chapter 2 System & Project Background

Artificial Intelligence for Predictive Maintenance

Artificial Intelligence is a sector in the computing industry that aims to help automate tasks, inform and most importantly help people and systems in everyday life. Advancements in this sector have led to large improvements in accessibility for all people to services, improving policing and consumer computing but not so much outside of the house. Artificial Intelligence is yet to be widely implemented for consumers in a way that can help improve their lives, reduce costs and improve physical accessibility. There are higher-end artificial intelligence models that specifically can adapt their learning based on updated and improved data in real-time often such as neural networks which are becoming increasingly common on vehicles with an active internet connection (Susto et al., 2015).

Artificial Intelligence has been slowly implemented in the automotive industry and despite representing a pivotal moment in the upkeep of vehicles, often are made to be proprietary and rarely provides any useful data to the end user. Larger organisations such as Formula 1 and companies with fleets to manage have been heavily involved in developing ways in which artificial intelligence can help reduce downtime and provide a clear concise overview of vehicle health. As with most sectors, this will make a shift to the consumer market but is predominantly for businesses with the ability to develop large scale highly accurate models.

Data-driven Vehicle Maintenance

Manufacturers currently implementing systems to help owners reduce downtime are often proprietary because of the competitive nature of the car industry and therefore the ability to “lockdown” systems allows them to control and secure their income as it is often limited information provided to an end-user or even a local garage. A multitude of manufacturers develop custom tools that only authorized service providers can use to understand the issues that a vehicle’s onboard diagnostic system is reporting. Although a universal tool that connects to an industry-standard onboard diagnostic port (OBD Port) can be used even by consumers to read vehicle error codes, this is an example of reactive or proactive maintenance, not predictive. This is because a vehicle’s OBD system only reports faults after they have occurred or warnings when items are already beginning to fail – not containing any logic or understanding of patterns to warn users of potential failures.

A key to a manufacturer's ability and commercial sectors to complete such accurate models is primarily due to the improvements and developments in sensors and sensor fusion technology. They allow for in-depth real-time data to be collected from a multitude of different systems and sections of the car which are used together to provide a machine learning model with an idea of the current system's performance that is detailed enough to make any small difference in readings accurate enough to suggest a problem. This is a massive improvement in predictability because of the real-time data processing that occurs. Previously, only past data, services, and MOTs were available for a car. Previously, there has not been an attempt to utilise this data widely in terms of a machine learning model to predict parts that will fail an MOT for a certain year.

Project Sources

An anonymized dataset is available from the United Kingdom Government website under an open government license that provides details about tests, their related vehicles and the specific parts information. In total, 76 GB of raw data shows a detailed view of over 500 million MOT tests ranging in a broad spectrum of makes, models and other variables such as mileages. Overall, the combination of the entire dataset can help to provide a comprehensive overview of a lot of vehicle's health status. Using a trained model, it should become easy to see and represent vehicles with outlying features and classifications such as continuous problems or repetitive failures of certain parts within a specific vehicle identification or a specific brand or model.

Additionally, there is a DVLA REST API which is publicly available for projects which will help to dynamically request and gain vehicle information as well as reduce stress on a particular server as it outsources data queries of a vehicle database to the Government content distribution network. Unfortunately, the problem with this is that it is not compatible with the MOT data set due to the anonymity.

Open-source and freely available software solutions can be used to train a model and implement the model for the use of consumers, namely, SciKit Learn provides a highly adaptable and impressive machine learning training software for use in Python which scales well, especially with large datasets such as the aforementioned one.

Project Challenges

As aforementioned, the project aims to use a more native form of machine learning utilizing prior knowledge and data sets and relying upon that data to provide predictions. Firstly, this limits the model as new vehicles typically do not have an MOT until they are three years old. This means that a lot of newer model cars are eradicated from the training dataset and leaves the model with only a manufacturer and mileage in terms of variables to use for predictions of future MOTs and until these newer vehicles become three years old, their data won't be available through the project database service.

Additionally, due to the wide variety of different vehicles, training an accurate model to even predict the actual outcome of the test will be extremely difficult and it is likely to struggle with overfitting when attempting to cover a large amount of these vehicles or underfitting when working with a reduced amount of processing power and budgets. For such a widened data set, even a small percentage of accuracy is a large population of the data and it is expected that the combination of current data inputted by an end user with historical data will improve this accuracy level.

Additionally, the system will lack any direct communication with a vehicle, which opens it up to vulnerabilities with temperamental data due to user error especially when the data is translated from a vehicle through a user to the project system. The lack of real-time data sensors does depreciate the reliability and predictability of a vehicle's health.

Finally, the gap between consumers and garages suffers due to the aforementioned lack of consumer knowledge, a reduction in trust in these industries reduces end-users willingness to have their vehicle serviced as it is seen as an unnecessary step and therefore a barrier to completing predictive maintenance via the use of a technician's knowledge and observations.

The challenge of the overall system will be to use a wide range of sparse data to make generalized assumptions about a vehicle's health which will be overcome by the development of stages. Initially looking at purely a pass or fail result – this is expected to be the main objective of the project as accuracy is more paramount than detailed data. A pass or fail suggestion is enough to prompt a user to service their vehicle essentially completing at a minimum proactive maintenance before warnings appear.

Ethical & Legal Challenges

As with all publicly accessible computer systems and especially systems utilizing artificial intelligence to process individual data, there is a high degree of responsibility to process, store and secure data in a way that protects privacy and reliably so that data is not lost.

Furthermore, the implementation of machine learning with user vehicles carries a safety responsibility ethically as it may lead to making different decisions that may improve or decrease the safety of a vehicle.

Data collection and processing must conform to the general data protection regulation (GDPR) by collecting only the data necessary, protecting that data, and offering redundancy and availability to the end users. Given that this is a web-hosted project there is both a legal obligation and ethical obligation to meet the GDPR requirements.

This project overcomes most concerns with data safety and protection by using the latest web-industry standard framework and utilizing standard industry practices such as hashing passwords before storage to prevent data leakage even if there were to be an exploit on the internal database .

Project Scope

The project-specific scope is minuscule in comparison to the entirety of the automotive industry. Potentially, a well-trained well-implemented system has the potential to massively improve the consumer-garage relationships whilst improving downtime and costs dramatically. It could if on a much wider scope have the potential to decrease failures in MOT testing figures for the DVLA. Due to both time constraints and also hardware constraints, it would be impractical to be able to train a well-formulated model without using expensive third-party servers. Additionally, due to cost restraints, the project can only work on a small scale and therefore cannot promise to improve or enhance vehicle reliability or even safety. Even at a small scale, the ideology and implementations of the project are a stepping stone to a much bigger and more widespread issue that can be resolved. Expanding upon this specific scope, further implementations could grow to contain wider datasets and accept further information with integration with OBD II devices which allow for a user reading of a car's diagnostic system or even a way to integrate with embedded sensors and data as they become more open source. This specific project scope can more easily be expanded with service recording being integrated to offer a much more full picture of the vehicle's overall health.

Chapter 3 Literature Review

Predictive maintenance, that being a maintenance schedule carried out from a recommendation of repairs and services based on a vehicle's behaviour and health has so far been a task which is carried out by few people and has been completed in a knowledge-based way a vehicle technician usually uses their observations and their experiences to recommend parts, cleaning and servicing. There are grave inefficiencies with these processes, namely having to take a vehicle to a repair & service centre before work can be carried out – this process consumes a significant amount of time, money and effort for end-users and usually is not a task that is considered critical unless it is a legally mandated MOT test (M. Paolanti et al.,).

The theoretical ideas of predictive maintenance have been heavily investigated and researched, specifically for the efficient methods of data collection and implementation into a variety of standardised machine learning models. There is no shortage of research and development in the predictive maintenance sector for consumer vehicles, but a gap in how to bridge the theoretical research of the systems and the ability to implement it in a live working environment.

Throughout most research completed recently, the predictive maintenance research has almost solely focused on utilising machine learning models – particularly those that can be intensely trained on past data (which is also classified as off-board data) such as the aforementioned MOT and even servicing history which can help to identify patterns in a vehicle's health. Utilising machine learning can employ mathematical modelling within the issue to classify and detect outliers which are representative of what could be inferred as 'warning signs' for vehicles and their maintenance. This does require a vast amount of data to ensure accuracy but this is not feasible as it is time-consuming and expensive to ensure a variety of sensors are installed throughout the vehicle – a problem which predictive maintenance aims to prevent. Whether the data provided for the training of the machine learning model be live or on-board data or health history of the vehicle – a model can only be expected as accurate if it has an identifier for what is considered working correctly and being in a faulty condition. For MOT records in the United Kingdom, this is completed through suggestions such as advisories and ultimately if a vehicle fails. A classification of pass and fail results should display significantly different results between them – but not always. Even if vehicles are to gain advisories which are highly relevant and helpful to modelling issues with

vehicles – these are not publicly available under the Open Government license and rather have to be found on a vehicle-by-vehicle basis, again making this impractical (M. Paolanti et al.,).

Another methodology investigated during previous research into bridging the gaps between the theoretical idea and the active implementation of a system involved the use of simulation that uses models built of either components or vehicles and used to monitor and therefore predict failures with the vehicles. Similarly to the current vehicle's integrated sensors being proprietary to a manufacturer, this approach can also be seen as the same – many manufacturers will test new vehicles, designs and components in computer-based simulation testing to predict failures and also test their initial applicability within the whole project. One wider issue based around simulation-based testing is that it is commonly testing without any degree of uncertainty – specifically the physics and material properties of car components are tested as if they are in an ideal world – which means that it is much less likely to report a potential fault on a vehicle than it would be if it used machine learning to identify future 'events'. Whilst machine learning additionally can use mass amounts of computing resources and even supercomputers, simulating a vehicle is limited much more to at minimum a basis where it is classified based on model and manufacturer, whereas training an artificial intelligence model can encapsulate all of these under one entire model efficiently without having to manually prepare alternatives for a change in these variables (Voronov, 2020).

A critical role in bringing this theoretical system to market is ensuring that the employed machine learning system is trained and implemented with the correct techniques and even specifications by using appropriate models and deducing given specific data what combination of specific training elements gives the most accurate results.

A barrier within the system and bringing it to market is an ethical barrier. Vehicles have the power to ultimately end life but alternatively have the power to increase accessibility massively. It would not be unusual for people to be sceptical around the idea of giving machine learning capabilities access to their vehicle – especially for more advanced solutions that more and more car manufacturers are embedding within them such as always-connected internet control systems which people see as weakness that could open their car up to attacks and vulnerabilities. Even a system that uses historical data can increase wariness due to the idea that if an error is to occur with their car due to unregulated and untested advice of a model, this could end in fatalities due to misinformation. It's important that at a minimum users be warned

about an artificially intelligent model when making suggestions and attempting to predict information about a vehicle as it could lead them to unnecessarily increase spending on their vehicle or neglect their vehicle further as it cannot be certified or guaranteed correct for all of the different scenarios provided to it.

Some important case studies are looking into predictive maintenance that helps to address the ethical issues raised in an alternative way by making the model more prone to recognizing hazards and failures when it comes to predicting the test results of a vehicle.

Models could potentially use a 'proportional-hazards' version which has baselines for warnings and when errors potentially begin occurring. This is important because for this purpose it is much more important to be overly cautious than nonchalant. Additionally, it is suggested that this software should be mere guidance in optimizing the decisions and processes which engineers and technicians go through when managing vehicles rather than an all-in-one solution. This element of the software is paramount – important to not discourage users from visiting an authorized mechanic with experience but rather help the user understand when and also why a vehicle might need to be seen by a specialist potentially more than what it currently is.

When utilizing a model for predictive analysis for the automotive industry, using past data means that the process the model goes through to reach a goal trickles through sub-criteria and decision goals. The decision as to where variables are classified in the importance of making an accurate decision is determined mathematically and can be calculated using libraries which are built into certain open-source models such as SciKit Learn. For a high-intensity intricate system of predictive maintenance, decision variables would include factors such as previous failure items, number of failures on specific vehicle parts, and potentially even the make and model if there are to be patterns recognized between those vehicles. Sub-criteria could indicate potentially less directly relevant variables such as the owner of a vehicle, an advanced system could potentially overview the history of car repair and servicing from a specific user to pick up on patterns such as maintenance required because of their driving behaviors leading to an increased likelihood of needing replacement parts. Figure __ shows the hierarchy of this model when utilised for predictive maintenance and how specifically they relate to each other. For a less advanced model, important factors which are accessible through open databases would indicate that decision variables would potentially include mileage, which would have a sub-criteria of vehicle age as in most cases these would be

correlated (although not a guarantee) which is why the actual mileage would be the decision variable (Arena et al., 2022).

Figure 1 Hierarchical Model of Machine Learning Decision Variables

(Carnero, 2005)

In overall consideration, the potential for predictive maintenance is gigantic, but the setbacks and potential problems that need to be overcome in implementing it accurately, ethically and in a user-friendly way will overcome trust issues and scepticism as aforementioned. Unlike some industries where specific machine learning models can be employed and excel at a particular item, it is clear that a combination of cautious features, models and additional libraries need to be employed in a product to ensure safety as well as accuracy.

Chapter 4 Problem Analysis

In the current market, consumers have a disconnect with garages, car maintenance and a lack of trust between advisors and consumers. There are systems in place that are designed to help users maintain their vehicles utilizing a multitude of sensors and combining them with the use of sensor fusion to deliver a service which is highly accurate in terms of vehicle maintenance but also comes at a high price from the proprietary software of vehicle manufacturer's. Ultimately, this defeats the purpose of saving time and money whilst improving and maintaining the safety of vehicles on the road. It additionally drives a wedge between technicians and consumers as they often give obscured data that drives consumers to trust specialist centres.

One of the major problems that this project addresses is the uncertainty that consumers have and their misinformation about the health of their vehicle and the requirements to ensure that it is properly and safely maintained. Commonly, cars are left un-serviced and rather left for their annual MOT. Whilst an MOT is useful in ensuring road safety, it cannot be a guarantee of car health for an entire year. As an MOT is completed in a short time, there are concise records that paint a snapshot of the car's health which can be manipulated by the user and as no further investigation is taken or warranted it can often miss underlying problems which would cause significant issue in the future of the vehicle. The problem is needing to inform consumers of how they can look after their vehicle and ensure its performance for the entire life span, not necessarily to instruct them to take care of items by themselves but particularly to ensure that it gets the necessary improvements.

Expanding upon this, the disconnect between garages and consumers has widened as there is a common stigma that garages are likely to 'rip off' customers for services which they don't need. The project aims to address this problem by creating direct links between vehicle owners and the garages which share vehicle diagnostics through the software to ensure that both sides are not only on the same page but additionally the consumer can feel trust in the advice given by a garage and be confident in receiving a service that they need. The connection of garages to the machine learning element allows for a more detailed observation to be included in considerations of the results for vehicles and allows for an easy exchange of this information to an accessible user-friendly web page.

With the DVLA in the United Kingdom, a lot of data is anonymized and a lot is redacted making it difficult to build a system around the idea of maintaining and tracking a car's health. The problem is addressable with the correct methods and procedures to turn obscured data into

usable data – providing the user can source certain information about their vehicle. This problem is necessary to address as without previous history of a vehicle, it is not necessarily feasible. In addition to this information, the ability to track external records such as write-off records or crash records would be an impediment, however, there isn't an easily accessible way to gather this information for cars.

A further challenge comes as the development of the automotive industry has strived to increase the market for electric vehicles and hybrid vehicles. Whilst some combustion engines may contain differing components, they are usually generic and almost all vehicles can be covered by the full range of failure items that the DVLA refer to. However, with these different technologies, they may omit some elements that a combustion vehicle has and will have extra parts. Therefore the model has an issue of needing to identify what type of vehicle it is and appropriately predicting what elements to recommend servicing. Trust will be lost in the product if it were to recommend a traditional car part as a potential advisory on a fully electric vehicle (Santos and Daniel, 2008).

Finally, with considerations of these rapidly changing car markets, it leaves the industry of MOT testing to also change drastically and update significantly to make it more relevant to newer technology. Therefore there needs to be a modular approach taken to the service to allow items such as just the machine learning model to be updated if certain decision factors are changed or replaced for MOT testing, and it needs to be able to adapt more importantly dynamically for the recording and storing of data if it becomes apparent that further or differing information will be used for future MOT testing.

Overall, the main problems that the system needs to address are to inspire consumer confidence in garages, inform consumers of their vehicle requirements and have the adaptability to continue to be relevant.

Chapter 5 System Requirements

System requirements are imperative to the success of a project and critically define how, when and what a system does and behaves when being operated. A detailed system requirement layout will ensure that milestones are met and application functions are implemented correctly and appropriately.

Using a standard success criterion ensures that the project is working to meet the overall aim and objectives, to create a web-based software that allows for the reading and writing of car service information with the ability to use machine learning on past data and provide predictions of necessary car maintenance that needs to be completed and predict the result of the upcoming results.

The primary success criteria of the project will be the creation of a publicly hosted web-based app with the necessary features to allow the project to be completed. Firstly, the web application needs to be developed with consistent style and formatting without any accessibility issues. It needs to be clear and concise – allowing for the main functionalities; login, signup and the public predictive maintenance feature. The success criteria should mean that regardless of whether a user has an account or does not, they should have access to the machine learning aspect of the application to allow freely accessible requests to be made. This is in line with the ethos of the project which allows consumers to gain a better understanding of their vehicles. Using a web application helps to ensure compatibility with a range of devices and doesn't use proprietary coding languages for specific operating systems.

The system requires the ability to log in and sign up, allowing users to maintain their vehicles and an account record to allow further ease of access. This should also allow for users to be classified as a user or a garage, and allow a linking between the two different types of accounts. There should be strict access implementation between the accounts to ensure that the project adheres to the general data protection regulations.

Furthering on the compliance with GDPR, the website needs to ensure that security measures are implemented and a strong firewall such as Cloudflare to protect the web server against potentially dangerous attacks which could expose private data to the public.

The system needs to have the ability to access an external REST API service which will allow for the requests of information about vehicles and allow for the responses about their predictive test results and other information.

With this, there must be a REST API created which serves the machine learning model so that it can be queried by the web application and deliver the results back to the controller of the Laravel project.

Finally, the entirety of the system needs to work to a low latency to prevent customers from becoming unhappy with the software and also keep the element of accessibility by not having issues with freezing. This step requires regular testing and checking to keep it in line with typical standards for a web-served application.

Chapter 6 System Design

Graphical User Interface Design

Because of the complex nature of the software solution and the variety of users targeted with the web-platform solution, a clean, consistent and accessible format that is easy to read and understand is paramount to the success of the application.

As previously mentioned, the design of the system needs to be clean and accessible – this is attempting to account for all people with any visual impairments or mental impairments, this again acts in a way to maximize trust and accessibility.

Alongside this, consistency is a key element of the design nature of the project, using a framework allows a custom layout that has been developed to be recalled and imported into every different implementation of a view window – ensuring consistency stays entirely correct with no room for error.

The graphical user interface design also needs to ensure flexibility to ensure compatibility with a range of devices for which styling classes with tailwind are used to maintain a clean style and flexibility in this manner. Alongside this, the user interface must remain lightweight because of the aforementioned loading times and accessibility.

Styling of the website will use highly contrasting colours including a dark background, white text and a ‘traffic-light’ colour coding system which allows for easy understanding even without having to necessarily read the text displayed. In this same methodology, icons are employed to help with understanding and provide a visual aid to end-users who may have issues with vision.

Navigationally, the website will also use a classic navigation bar with a header and footer with the main content being sandwiched in between, this brings a familiarity and ease-of-use advantage with everything being in a pre-expected location. Appendix 1 displays the consistent styling across multiple pages and throughout the whole website. It additionally shows the simplicity of the website and how integrations such as an API are similarly formatted and integrated to present a consistent website that appears as one single service

Process Design

System Architecture & Framework

The architecture of the entirety of the system is encapsulated within a Laravel framework, a constantly maintained, updated and secure framework designed specifically for PHP and web

development. The framework introduces a system architecture with a hierarchical methodology to the design of the processes which occur within it. There are several different layers including views, routes, controllers and data management as well as an overall environment controller layer (Laravel, n.d.).

Primarily, the view layer of the system architecture is the raw HTML and CSS styling elements that allow the website to be built and programmed like any other website that doesn't utilise a framework. With the view layer, it reduces it to purely the visual elements and items such as forms, this makes data management much more secure as processes are not completed within the view window which is opened on the client device. This helps with data and process separation.

The routes layer defines what web addresses, posts and get requests are directed where, this is the middle layer between the views and controllers and also integrates middleware which allows for certain routes to be denied or allowed based on conditions such as a user logged in or not. Further to that, the controller layer receives any data passed through the POST/GET requests from the view layer and completes the data processing and handling which is defined in the code, passing it back to the view after completion.

Finally, wrapped in the Laravel framework, the environment controller sets up important elements such as a production or development platform and database connections and credentials.

The process design of the system architecture is defined by the framework used and helps to maintain consistent, safe operations within a public domain environment (Ahern, Dominic and Bruton, 2022).

Data Collection & Data Management

The data collection process consists of several varying steps which are different along different time scales of the application.

For the propagation of the database and initial machine learning testing, all of the anonymous data sets and lookup tables are collected utilizing a multi-threaded custom Python downloader to import all of the data into .csv files. During this propagation phase, these data files have to be pre-conditioned to ensure that they can be imported and managed correctly – python has been used again with a custom-written script to achieve this.

Data ingestion uses open source software for propagation in the form of DBeaver which allows for reliable data importation from CSV files which has no expiration time, unlike phpmyadmin. This data collection stands for the initial creation of the database in which the aforementioned

framework can also use gitbash to control the 'migrations' and creation of database tables where data is eventually imported (Hu et al., 2023).

Data collection also occurs throughout the life of the final system, with registering users, registering cars, linking vehicles and customer car details with an MOT method and further collecting data when predictions are created (Transport, Department for, 2022).

Data processing happens at the initialization phase to make sure that the data is in an easy-to-manage-to-manage format which will ensure data integrity and a 3rd Normal Form.

Predictive API Modelling and Interaction Process

Similarly to the process designed for data collection and management, the predictive element (machine learning element) utilises a custom Python script with a standard training library 'SciKit Learn'. For which the process of this is to retrieve the data from the importation phase, then separate this data into numerical and categorical elements and normalize data such as manufacturers and models so that it applies to a model. The model then utilises a mathematical linear regression with classifiers to model all of the results, comparing and contrasting them to identify outliers and patterns that occur in a vehicle's health history. This can then be re-used to ensure that when entering further information it is accurate. When training the model, the process of development also includes automatic testing usually at a ratio of 80% for training and 20% of the imported data set used for testing the accuracy of that model.

Based on the results of the output from these Python scripts, the elements of the model and certain features can be adapted and updated with somewhat trial and error with each of the aspects. Each time the training is re-run new statistics are developed for the accuracy and recall amounts of each element that the algorithm is attempting to predict.

Once a model is created, a label classifier and the model can be exported, the label classifier acting as a dictionary for the results that are exported by running the model.

Finally, an implementation of the 'waitress' library in Python which takes the model and the dictionary allows for JSON queries and returns a response using the model on the given data.

This fits into the website as an external service and allows for a model to be updated over time without impacting the website application.

User interaction and output design

As touched upon within the design of the system framework and overview, the user interaction with the application follows a traditional process design. Starting at an index page, having a branch for authentication (as part of an authentication controller) which includes pages including login, logout, register and delete for the account. Then there are main pages including, cars, account details and the page for predictive maintenance. For business accounts, this hierarchy is slightly different as cars are superseded by customers with cars being an element below the customer on this page. The interaction follows a traditional process as well – particularly for the predictive maintenance element of the website. Starting with entering vehicle data, that is being checked and implemented and then utilizing logic to display an additional page if necessary to locate the government vehicle ID for the car then the results are presented on a clean page with an overall pass/fail prediction and also a prediction for advisories or any issues that might appear relating to the vehicle. All of the output designs are processed through the controllers and outputted within the HTML elements that are passed through as variables.

System integration and future maintenance

The design process for the system integration allows for existing work processes and workflows followed by places such as commercial garages to add this to their workflow with very little extra work but also integrates to offer a high level of detail to allow customer cars to be checked by a garage, whereas the existing government system provides this on a real-time access basis rather than the ability to do so in advance. The system is designed in modular parts to allow one single update to change the design, views and predictive maintenance elements. DNS caching using a Cloudflare account allows for major maintenance to take place whilst DNS servers resolve the website to a cache to minimize disruption and downtime.

Chapter 7 System Implementation

Development Stack

For the system implementation, as touched upon utilises industry standards for a web application and the development of it. Using standardized HTML and CSS for the page content, views and layout although these are saved in a .blade.php file due to the framework chosen for this specific project. All files are as a .php model and it uses models rather than just variables to manage items from controllers to communicating with the database. This is due to the framework used; Laravel. Laravel helps provide consistent structuring for PHP-based applications and helps to fast-track the creation of features such as authentication. Additionally, the framework aids in the creation of a database and its management, with migration files which communicate with MySQL or Postgresql so that it is set correctly every time and also allows the framework to use the data in these as it is as expected from the propagation elements within Laravel (Laravel, 2024).

IDE and Management Tools

The development of this process used GitBash as a command line interface to control the Laravel framework and this tool was implemented within the terminal section of Visual Studio Code insiders.

Visual Studio code was chosen as it hosts several add-ons which apply to the development of PHP applications and help expedite the process. In addition to this, the addition of GitBash also offers version control which was linked to GitHub Desktop to help keep track of improvements and allow rollbacks throughout the development process. For data implementation; PhpMyAdmin was used for central management of the database; Laravel was used for the setup and the open-source DBeaver software was included for the ease-of-use features when inserting large files of csvs into the SQL database.

Software deployment and security

The software was deployed using a Lampp stack using Apache and MySQL services to allow for an easy all-in-one hosting platform which was implemented on a personal server and set up for access with port forwarding through a static IP address. To enhance security and give detailed analytics of the website, Cloudflare was employed as the DNS registrar for the website hosted at www.progarageportal.co.uk where it first completes a captcha check before proxying the connection to the web server. This conceals the identity of the server whilst maintaining security and allowing for easy additions of security rules and firewall configurations.

Implementation Process

The process was followed by ensuring all prerequisites were met including the installation of Python, relevant libraries, IDE and the Lampp stack to host the websites locally for the phase of development and testing. Once this was completed a Laravel project could be initialized with the php artisan create command which created the directory and the outline of the project. Uploading the source files onto the final production server and changing the environment variables to 'production' secures the data and prevents errors from being sent back to users. Then routing the Cloudflare DNS server to point at ports:80 and:443 on the server. By using Zerossl the connection between the server and client is encrypted for free with an official SSL certificate.

Chapter 8 System Testing

The development processes implemented a rapid-prototyping model in which a full working prototype was developed at the end of each cycle, whether this be a prototype of a specific module that works within the system or an overall prototype (Upcraft and Fletcher, 2003).

Testing is one of the most important aspects of the development life cycle – the process that allows for testing of accuracy and the ability of a system to work to the desired specifications. It also allows for the system to be fixed and rectified before pushing it out to the general public. At the forefront of system testing, it prevents execution of malicious actors such as through SQL injection and at the latter it can be used to ensure that colours and different resolutions display the application correctly. The iterative model utilised for the development of this application continuously tests throughout the development and tests not only at the milestone of each iteration but even the components that are within it.

Testing Methodology

Due to time limitations given the rapid development of the application, rather than a mixture of automated and manual testing on the application, manual testing is a lot easier to complete particularly if it is in small steps during the development (Asfaw, D., 2015). Regardless of the lack of automated testing, manual testing still captures the entire system from specific elements to the entirety of the system working together as one unit. Testing will test all elements from design to processes and security.

As previously mentioned, the testing of the system begins with unit testing. This type of testing is done throughout the development of the source code and is used to help guide and complete sections of the application (Shahabuddin, S.M. and Prasanth, Y., 2016.). This development was completed in both the browser and within the IDE testing through a graphical user interface and the command line interface combined to ensure that both backend and frontend systems were working as individual units rather than testing as a whole.

After a successful trial of unit testing, the testing methodology transfers to testing the system when components have to begin communicating with each other (Shahabuddin, S.M. and Prasanth, Y., 2016.). In this instance, this represents how a route would request a controller to return a blade file (html view window) and ensure that this worked correctly passing through the correct variables and information to the view window (Laravel, n.d.). Additionally, this is completed when ensuring that the MySQL server software and the Laravel framework are

configured correctly and CRUD operations can be completed successfully back and forth between the database. An external factor of the custom REST API also meant that the data transport had to be tested going from a Laravel view and being returned to a Laravel view – even before the API was linked to the database. Linking an API between the database and itself was similarly tested as a sandbox test to ensure the basics were functioning correctly.

After integration has occurred from the successful results of testing, the system is tested as one unit. This testing requires a lot of complexity because a mixture of different systems and programming languages are being used together. Ultimately, system testing is much more than loading up the website locally and testing all of the features work. Logging is an important part of this element that allows insight. This is an important part because systems can appear to function correctly whilst handling errors with exceptions that make them appear to be okay. These errors can be a cause for concern because they may allow security vulnerabilities within the system or may result in the system malfunctioning in some use-case scenarios.

Testing should be carried out by user testing additionally, whilst the developer knows how the system should act and perform, to ensure that the success criteria are met for accessibility and ease of use, new subjects should be able to interact with the software and be able to use it without running into difficulties or errors. Commonly, an end user will be able to discover or uncover a bug which a developer misses due to their fluency in the final software developed.

Known Issues

As with any system, there are known minor bugs or issues that are unresolved and therefore are known improvements to be made to the system. None of the known issues provided present any data integrity issues or even security issues but do impact how the application should run against the success criteria.

Primarily, due to the large dataset provided, using an SQL table with more than 30 million entries (approximately the value of 1 year's worth of MOTs) causes a significant impact on the latency of a website and impacts the user experience drastically. Switching to a more robust database engine would fix this issue but involve time that is currently unavailable.

The machine learning module that was trained had to be trained on a limited data set giving it only the ability to predict the test result and not advisories or warnings – this is down to both a

storage and computational power limit. Because of this, it contains a 7% accuracy limit for predicting test failures but a 77% accuracy limit for test passes.

Chapter 9 Project Conclusion

Critical Evaluation

Overall, this project aimed to create a machine learning software and platform to access this machine learning model to enable a freely accessible system to inform and help users maintain their vehicles and help prevent bad vehicle safety by increasing services and repairs when and if necessary, by predicting future issues and MOT tests based on historical and concurrent data provided between the government and consumers. The aims and objectives of this project are listed in appendix 2 where it is clear that a major goal of the software is to enable a connection and inspire trust between consumers and garages to help promote predictive maintenance both with artificial intelligence and also with human expertise and knowledge from service providers.

Key goals that were accomplished throughout the creation of this project include the development of a user-friendly, highly accessible web-based application, which is working for both consumer and garage accounts. Additionally, a Python-based REST API was successfully created, trained and implemented seamlessly into the web application that contains some accuracy for test fails and significant accuracy for test passes.

Whilst ensuring that the project met all of the written criteria at a minimum, there were significant improvements that could be made to allow the project to work better and deliver a better service for users. The machine learning model is the largest downfall of the service. It essentially completes the task at hand but lacks clarity and accuracy. Based on the data given, it struggled to find classifications and outliers due to the skew of the data leaving a precision of 0.07% and 0.77%. It was seen that with a smaller data set and more variables including failure items, it was able to achieve an average of 87% between pass and fails which is impressive and leads belief that there is great potential for modelling with a linear regression. This model could not be implemented as shown in Figure ___ since it was grossly underfitted to the entirety of the dataset used.

```
[13] ✓ 3m 28.2s
```

...	precision	recall	f1-score	support
ABA	1.00	0.75	0.86	4
ABR	0.76	0.51	0.61	43
F	0.90	0.86	0.88	9198
P	0.84	0.92	0.88	9356
PRS	0.93	0.63	0.75	1399
accuracy			0.87	20000
macro avg	0.89	0.73	0.80	20000
weighted avg	0.87	0.87	0.87	20000

A scalable cloud-hosted service would have been much more efficient and applicable to the development of this system as it would have allowed for fast processing of intense data training for the machine learning model and would have potentially opened the door to include extra features such as predicting advisories and predicting failure items.

Regrettably, although the final design and view window elements are considered accessible, real-world end-user testing would have consolidated this much further and could have opened an opportunity to improve the system drastically for the wide variety of users which it had been designed for.

Further Development

Further development of the web-based application would likely take the form of organizing the data structure as a priority ensuring that a more robust data engine is used that doesn't impose long dwell times when loading the application. After data issues had been completed, the main focus would be to develop the machine learning module even further given that the actual website has already been coded to allow elements such as advisories passed from the JSON queries of the machine to be interpreted.

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Consistent View Window Styling

Figure 2 Index Page View

Figure 3 Sign up form view

Figure 4 Login form view

Figure 5 Javascript warnings

Figure 6 Javascript Notifications

Figure 7 Cars Index View

Figure 8 Account Index View

Figure 9 AI API Information

Figure 10 Locate vehicle ID based off of MOT record form

Figure 11 API results returned view

Appendix 2 – Previously listed aims and objectives

Aim	
To create a web-based software that allows for the storage and recording of car servicing and test information containing the ability to interpret past data and provide estimations on upcoming car servicing to both end-user consumers and garages to help prevent breakdowns before they occur and therefore save time and money.	
Objectives	
1	Setup a development web-hosting environment using XAMPP software on a Linux virtual machine allocating enough resources to allow for machine learning and mathematical algorithms. This can be completed within the first day, as the configuration of the server is the basis for which everything else will run on
2	To Investigate a number of car service histories and create a flat file database with this information to track a timeline of breakdown and issues. This objective should allow for a variety of suitable data sets to be selected for the forthcoming objectives of the development of the system. The investigation needs to be completed by the first week of the project, potentially with the collection of information being started before the project is begun.
3	To develop an SQL database by collecting all MOT data from the government website, normalising the data and creating a script to import the data into the database. Additional

	<p>data such as service history should also be included in this SQL database and users, this is the basis in which the whole system will run on. This needs to be completed in the first week and may be stretched into the second week given the vast computing power and time required to create such a large database</p>
4	<p>To investigate and develop a machine learning model to identify a regression model for the normal behaviour of vehicles recorded in the SQL database and use examples from the service history to train the model on anomalies pointing to breakdowns (Intel, 2024). This should be completed in the initial weeks of the setup of the project as the following objectives cannot be completed after this</p>
5	<p>Test the model created using volunteers surveyed for their cars service history and record the reliability and adjust training on the model as is relevant. This objective should be completed over the bulk of the project for approximately 3-4 weeks as the effectiveness and the accuracy of the model is paramount.</p>
6	<p>Create a web interface by packaging the entire system allowing for it to be easily deployed and easily hosted as an online platform. This should be completed in the last 2 weeks of development as it is least complex and rather effects the accessibility rather than the usability</p>
7	<p>Record and assess the predictions and mathematical calculations of the model through the progression throughout the development process. Ensuring all code is documented by CIS3161 Project Proposal Caimen Thaine Jackson Page 6 of 15 commenting thoroughly. Test the model for performance and reliability recording findings and also critically assessing the project as a whole (BCS Higher Education Qualifications, 2020; X. Yu, W. Liu and J. Yang, 2020). This should be completed throughout the duration of the development and should be finished by the final week of the project.</p>

Table 1 Aims and Objections (Jackson C, 2024)

Appendix 3 – Cloudflare Security

Figure 12 Cloudflare Firewall for progarageportal.co.uk

Appendix 4 – Testing and Development

Figure 13 Testing MariaDB connection

Figure 14 Installation of Sci Kit Learn Package

Figure 15 SQL Database Normalisation Version 1

Figure 16 SQL Database Normalisation Version 2

```
28     make VARCHAR(255),
29     model VARCHAR(255).

PROBLEMS  OUTPUT  DEBUG CONSOLE  TERMINAL  PORTS

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 ~/Documents/dft_test_result_2023
$ split -l 500000 test_result.csv data_split_
split: cannot open 'test_result.csv' for reading: No such file or directory

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 ~/Documents/dft_test_result_2023
$ split -l 500000 test_result.csv data_split_

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 ~/Documents/dft_test_result_2023
$ █
```

Figure 17 Splitting 3gb CSV Files

```
engine_size: 171,
mileage: "102000",
}

> \App\Models\Car::find(1)->user
= App\Models\User {#5066
  id: 1,
  name: "Caimen",
  email: "pikwhizz101@gmail.com",
  email_verified_at: "2024-03-04 02:26:22",
  #password: "$2y$12$cCGVaqfksQI/aCGe.M2dk.WmW0.Q6E0ZFHD/wRKu4eYk6VX.AytLa",
  address: "fsafasf",
  date_of_birth: "4200-07-08",
  license_type: null,
  license_updated: "2000-02-01",
  user_type: "consumer",
  business_name: null,
  #remember_token: null,
  created_at: "2024-03-04 02:26:22",
  updated_at: "2024-03-04 02:26:22",
}

> █
```

Figure 18 Laravel Unit Testing with Tinker

```
PROBLEMS  OUTPUT  DEBUG CONSOLE  TERMINAL  PORTS

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 /c/xampp/htdocs/carapp (master)
$ php artisan make:model vehicles -m

[INFO] Model [C:\xampp\htdocs\carapp\app\Models\vehicles.php] created successfully.

[INFO] Migration [C:\xampp\htdocs\carapp\database\Migrations\2024_03_03_223523_create_vehicles_table.php] created successfully.

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 /c/xampp/htdocs/carapp (master)
$ █
```

Figure 19 Laravel Database Migration & Propagation

```

form.blade.php U x web.php 1, M x
routes > web.php > ...
1 <?php
2
3 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Route;
4
5 /*
6 |-----
7 | Web Routes
8 |-----
9 |
10 | Here is where you can register web routes for your application. These
11 | routes are loaded by the RouteServiceProvider and all of them will
12 | be assigned to the "web" middleware group. Make something great!
13 |
14 */
15
16 // Route::get('/test', function() {
17 //     return view('test');
18 // });
19
20 // Route::get('/index', function() {
21 //     return view('index');
22 // });
23
24
25 Route::get('/', function () {
26     return view('index');
27 });
28
29 Route::get('/login', [UserController::class, 'login']->name('login')->middleware('guest'));
30
31

```

Figure 20 Demonstration of routes routing to controllers

```

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 /C
caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 /c/xampp/htdocs/carapp (master)
$ php artisan make:controller UserController

INFO Controller [C:\xampp\htdocs\carapp\app\Http\Controllers\UserController.php] created successfully.

```

Figure 21 Creation of controllers


```

app > Models > User.php > User > $fillable
9 use Laravel\Sanctum\HasApiTokens;
10
11 class User extends Authenticatable
12 {
13     use HasApiTokens, HasFactory, Notifiable;
14
15     /**
16      * The attributes that are mass assignable.
17      *
18      * @var array<int, string>
19      */
20     protected $fillable = [
21         'name',
22         'email',
23         'password',
24         'address', //add address field
25         'date_of_birth', //add dob field
26         'license_type', //add license_type field
27         'license_updated', //add license_granted field
28     ];
29
30     /**

```

Figure 22 Creation of models within the OOP Program

```

database > migrations > 2014_10_12_000000_create_users_table.php > class > up > Closure
4 use Illuminate\Database\Schema\Blueprint;
5 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Schema;
6
7 return new class extends Migration
8 {
9     /**
10      * Run the migrations.
11      */
12     public function up(): void
13     {
14         Schema::create('users', function (Blueprint $table) {
15             $table->id();
16
17             $table->string('name');
18             $table->string('email')->unique();
19             $table->timestamp('email_verified_at')->nullable();
20             $table->string('password');
21             $table->string('address')->nullable(); //Add address field
22             $table->date('date_of_birth')->nullable(); //adds date of birth
23             $table->enum('license_type', ['provisional', 'full manual', 'full automatic'])->nullable(); //Add license details
24             $table->date('license_updated')->nullable(); //Adds license granted date field
25             $table->rememberToken();
26             $table->timestamps();
27         });
28     }
29
30     /**
31      * Reverse the migrations.
32      */
33     public function down(): void
34     {
35         Schema::dropIfExists('users');
36     }
37 }

```

```

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIHBI MINGW64 /c/xampp/htdocs/carapp (master)
$ php artisan migrate

 INFO  Running migrations.

2014_10_12_000000_create_users_table ..... 61ms DONE
2014_10_12_100000_create_password_reset_tokens_table ..... 22ms DONE
2019_08_19_000000_create_failed_jobs_table ..... 48ms DONE
2019_12_14_000001_create_personal_access_tokens_table ..... 71ms DONE

caime@DESKTOP-F5FIHBI MINGW64 /c/xampp/htdocs/carapp (master)
$ █

```

Figure 23 Database Table setup

```

PROBLEMS OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS

c:\xampp\mysql\bin>mysql -u app_connect -p
Enter password: *****
Welcome to the MariaDB monitor.  Commands end with ; or \g.
Your MariaDB connection id is 737
Server version: 10.4.27-MariaDB mariadb.org binary distribution

Copyright (c) 2000, 2018, Oracle, MariaDB Corporation Ab and others.

Type 'help;' or '\h' for help. Type '\c' to clear the current input statement.

MariaDB [(none)]> CREATE DATABASE carapp;
Query OK, 1 row affected (0.001 sec)

MariaDB [(none)]> █

```

Figure 24 SQL Server Unit Testing

Figure 25 Initial Setup of laravel

Figure 26 Pre-requisite of lampp stack installation errors

Figure 27 Error Reporting

Figure 28 Configuration of windows vhosts

```
C:\xampp\apache\conf\extra\httpd-vhosts.conf - Notepad++ [Administrator]
File Edit Search View Encoding Language Settings Tools Macro Run Plugins Window ?
httpd-vhosts.conf hosts
55     DocumentRoot "C:/xampp/htdocs/fypapp/public"
56     ServerName fypapp.caimen
57     ##ServerAlias www.dummy-host.example.com
58     ##ErrorLog "logs/dummy-host.example.com-error.log"
59     ##CustomLog "logs/dummy-host.example.com-access.log" common
60 </VirtualHost>
61
62 <VirtualHost *:80>
63     ##ServerAdmin webmaster@dummy-host.example.com
64     DocumentRoot "C:/xampp/htdocs/carapp/public"
65     ServerName carapp.test
66     ##ServerAlias www.dummy-host.example.com
67     ##ErrorLog "logs/dummy-host.example.com-error.log"
68     ##CustomLog "logs/dummy-host.example.com-access.log" common
69 </VirtualHost>
70
71
72
```

Figure 29 Virtual Host configuration

```
caime@DESKTOP-F5FIH3I MINGW64 /c/xampp/htdocs
$ composer create-project laravel/laravel carapp
```

Figure 30 Initialisation of laravel app

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